

Panthera leo White lion (African lion)

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Mammal

Size:

Males:	Length: 2.5-3.3 m	Shoulder Height: 1.2 m	Mass: 150-225 kg
Females:	Length: 2.3-2.7 m	Shoulder Height: 1.0 m	Mass: 110-152 kg

Distribution:

The white lion is naturally restricted to the Timbavati–Greater Kruger region of northeastern South Africa, making it one of the most geographically localised large-mammal colour variants in the world.

Importance:

Lions are classified as vulnerable. The white lion is a naturally occurring colour variant caused by a recessive gene (leucism), not albinism. They are extremely rare, and their genomes have never been sequenced. Both the tawny and white lions are an important part of Kruger National Park's natural biodiversity.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 98.7 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 11.72 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 2.47 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 98.8% [Single: 93.3%, Duplicated: 5.5%]
BUSCO database: eukaryota
Assembly N50: 77 724.15 kilobases
Contig number: 286

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Date Published: 2026-04-22

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20339788>

